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Mapping Seasonal Access to Prenatal and Basic Emergency Obstetric in Cross River State, Nigeria.

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Abstract

Prenatal care and Basic Emergency Obstetric care (BEmOC) are essential sets of maternal health services which are delivered in the Primary Health Centres (PHCs) across Nigeria. Mapping of seasonal access to maternal health services are rarely considered in health-related studies, though maternal mortality remains a major problem in Nigeria. The objectives of this study are to map maternal population access to Prenatal and BEmOC, and examine its seasonality in Cross River State of Nigeria. The study included 960,361 females of childbearing age (15-49) and 119 government-managed primary health centres (PHCs). Data were sourced from secondary sources, and analysed using Geographical Information System (GIS) techniques. Drive times to PHCs were mapped by seasons, and multiple linear regression model was used to examine the relationship between drive times to the facilities, and socio-environmental factors. The results reveal declining maternal population access to healthcare in the wet season and significant relationship between seasonal drive times to maternal health services and socio-environmental factors. The ratios of access were 12.4 per 100,000 women and 7.0 per 100,000 in the dry wet seasons respectively. Facilities' access reduced from 100% in the dry season to 43.7% in the wet season. Average drive times in the dry and wet seasons were 41.1 minutes and 57.7 minutes respectively. Maternal population access to essential health services declines in the wet season due to flooding. Concerted effort should be made to increase maternal health care access in the wet season through sustainable planning and research.

Keywords: Mapping, Access, Maternal health, Health service.

Introduction

Maternal health services embody every dimension of health care required during the period of pregnancy, childbirth, and the postpartum period. These include; family planning, preconception, prenatal, childbirth and postnatal care. Lack of access to these services causes obstetric complications such as; haemorrhage, sepsis, complications of abortion, hypertensive disorders of pregnancy, prolonged/obstructed labour, ruptured uterus and ectopic pregnancy (World Health Organisation, 1996). Although some complications are unavoidable, timely access to a functioning healthcare which is absent in most developing countries may reduce the severity of

outcomes (Freedman et al., 2004). Therefore, a package of medical services named Emergency Obstetric Newborn Care (EmONC) was designed by the World Health Organisation (WHO), United Nations International Children's Emergency Fund (UNICEF) and United Nations Population Fund (UNFPA) to tackle the seven major obstetric complications (UNICEF, 1997). Facilities that provide the “signalling functions” such as; administration of parenteral antibiotics, oxytocic drugs and anticonvulsants, as well as manual removal of placenta, removal of retained products and assisted vaginal delivery are named Basic Emergency Obstetric Newborn Care (BEmONC). Facilities that perform all signalling functions, as well as Cesarean section and blood transfusion, are called Comprehensive Emergency Obstetric Newborn care (CEmONC).

Prenatal and BEmONC services are available in the Primary Health Centres (PHCs) across Nigeria and are managed by the local government authorities (Okoli et al., 2012). The Comprehensive EmONC services are provided in hospitals and managed by the state and federal governments (Bamgboye et al., 2015). This study focuses on the prenatal and Basic Emergency Obstetric Newborn Care (BEmONC) because it is the first line of maternal healthcare delivery.

Access is a fit between the client and the system (Penchansky & Thomas, 1981). It defines the ability to benefit from a service whenever it is needed. Access is influenced by the ability to pay, proximity, quantity and perception of the service. Thus, healthcare access is grouped into dimensions of finance, geography, availability and acceptability of the service (Peters et al., 2008). Access may be also hindered by physical barriers, lack of information, inadequate services, cultural and resource barriers (Adedini et al., 2014; World Health Organisation, 2018). Resource barriers are related to ability to pay for the service. Physical barriers are linked to the travel times or distance to the facilities. Cultural barriers refer to the practices that may enhance or hinder women from accessing maternal care. Such practices include religion, beliefs and social values relating to pregnancy and childbirth. However, the impact of resources and cultural barriers can be reduced if the physical barriers such as distance to the facilities are taken into consideration (Stock, 1983).

Excessive distance to health facilities increases the chances of delay in seeking medical care during pregnancy and childbirth. The WHO reported that poor women in the rural sub-Saharan Africa are least likely to receive adequate health care and only 40% of all pregnant women received the recommended antenatal care (World Health Organisation, 2018). Studies have found that the use of maternal health facilities for prenatal and childbirth decreases proportionately with distance (Heard et al., 2004; Matsuoka et al., 2010; Phiri et al., 2014). Delays in seeking maternal healthcare due to long distance to the facility were linked to haemorrhage, abortion and death (Almeida & Szwarcwald, 2012; Målqvist et al., 2010; Schoeps et al., 2011).

Approximately 15% of expected childbirths worldwide result in life-threatening complications during pregnancy, delivery, or the postpartum period (World Health Organisation, 1999). Globally, about 830 women die every day from pregnancy and childbirth-related causes which are preventable, and 99% of all the deaths occur in the developing countries (World Health Organisation, 2018). The WHO publication also reported that although maternal mortality globally dropped by 44% between 1990 and 2015, sub-Saharan Africa and South Asia still bear the highest burden of maternal mortality in the world. In 2015, 814 in 100,000 women in Nigeria died of pregnancy and childbirth-related causes, amounting to the second highest Maternal Mortality Ratio (MMR) in the world after India (World Health Organisation, 2015). However, some of the deaths are avoidable through access to transport, prompt diagnoses, low-cost treatment and health education (Ozumba & Nwogu-Ikojo, 2008). Geographical access to maternal health services such as prenatal and BEmOC remains a major problem in Nigeria and many developing countries (Adedini et al., 2014; World Health Organisation, 2018), and the problem exacerbates in the wet season.

The natural environment also plays a significant role in healthcare accessibility, human health and well-being (Bowler et al., 2010; Frumkin, 2001). Changes in weather and climate may cause diseases spread, change in lifestyle and limit transportation. During the winter in Europe, transport is usually limited due to severe snowfall. Similarly, the Springs or wet seasons' rainfalls in Africa cause flooding (Liu et al., 2012), which interrupts transport and access to healthcare. While the brute impact of flooding is being curtailed through better infrastructural development in the developed countries, the developing countries appear to be unprepared (Nkwunonwo et al., 2015). Surprisingly, most healthcare accessibility studies have given less consideration to geographical accessibility, let alone its seasonality. This present study argues that travel times increases in the wet season compared to the dry season due to flooding. This study links seasonal variability of geographical access with BEmOC, since it is one of the WHO recommendations for removing barriers to maternal health services (World Health Organisation, 2018).

Aims and Objectives

The aim is to examine seasonal variability of access to maternal healthcare in Cross River State. The objectives of this study are to map maternal population access to Prenatal and BEmOC, and examine its seasonality in Cross River State of Nigeria.

Material and Methods

The study was located in Cross River State (CRS), one of the 36 states of Nigeria (Figure 1). CRS is within the South-South Geopolitical zone and Niger Delta region. CRS is made of 1024 communities grouped into three senatorial districts namely: Southern Senatorial District (SSD), Northern Senatorial District (NSD) and Central Senatorial District (CSD). The state's population in 2015 was approximately 3.6 million. The area varies demographically and geographically, encompassing large rural areas such as Akpabuyo and Odukpani in the south with major conurbations such as Calabar, Ikom and Ogoja.

In 2015, women within child-bearing age (15-49 years) made up 26.5% of the state's population, indicating a critical need for access to maternal healthcare. Travels within CRS is limited by several factors including rainfall and topography. The tropical-humid climate in the state produces an average temperature between 15 - 30°C (Figure 2) resulting to annual rainfall of 1300-3000mm with highest peaks in the wet season which is usually between March and October (CometoNigeria, 2016; Njar et al., 2013). The topography which is generally flat and undulating (Water Supply and Sanitation Sector Reform Programme, 2016) encourages severe flooding in the wet season.

Figure 1: Study area map (Data Source: Office of the Surveyor-General of Cross River State)

Figure 2: Monthly Rainfall Averages of Calabar in 2019 (World Weather Online, 2017).

Heavy rainfalls in the wet season is usually followed by flooding of low-lying river basin communities (Moses, 1987; Nkwunonwo et al., 2015; Vanguard Nigeria, 2013). The flood usually remains unabated for a few minutes or throughout the wet season depending on the level of infrastructural development in the affected communities. The wet season is generally characterised by reduced mobility due to flooding of major roads (Figure 3). This study argues that population access to maternal health care in the wet season is usually interrupted in flood prone areas.

Whereas, other factors relating to maternal health services such as finance, cultural practices, quality of care and distance to service have been widely studied, mapping of seasonality of geographical access to maternal health care is not common in the literature. In Mozambique, access to maternal health services dropped by 9% and 5% by walking and public transport in the wet season, respectively (Makanga et al., 2017a). In Cross River State, the dry-wet season variation has never been studied, let alone examining the population at risk of losing access to maternal healthcare within that period.

Figure 3: Flooding of major roads and residential areas in Cross River State (Vanguard Nigeria, 2013)

Maternal health services are provided in all health facilities in Nigeria, except for purpose-built specialist health facilities such as the orthodontic, psychiatric and optical centres. Hospitals provide CEmONC and Primary Health Centres provide BEmONC. The Primary Health Centre (PHC) is the lowest level of healthcare and each is expected to serve up to 20,000 people (Obembe et al., 2017). Besides BEmONC, PHCs provide critical services including; health education, health promotions, antenatal care, post-natal care and distribution of Insecticide Treated Nets (ITN) (Obembe et al., 2017).

Data and Analyses

Secondary data sources were utilised for this study. GIS techniques and software were used for mapping of health facilities while relationships were analysed using regression models.

The data for PHCs, population, road network and socio-environmental factors were obtained from trusted government sources. A total of 119 PHCs were obtained from the Cross Rivers State Ministry of Health (CRSMoH) in an Excel file containing facilities' names and addresses. Since the facilities lacked location coordinates, the orthophoto map of CRS was used to assign location coordinates of communities to respective facilities. The use of communities' coordinates as proxies for facilities' coordinates is justified on the basis of lack of data and the presence of only one PHC in a community.

The road network was obtained from the office of the Surveyor-General Cross River State (OSG-CRS). It was edited where necessary to fix topological issues. A simple road network was built using ESRI ArcGIS Network Analyst tool. Although, the authors are aware of urban-rural driving speed variations, one travel speed was used for both urban and rural roads since there was no delineation of urban and rural roads in the original file. Average travel speed in Cross River

State was obtained by driving 3km through main roads and streets. The process was repeated in three distinct areas of the city and the average speed was calculated by dividing the total distance covered by travel time. Since some travel routes in Cross River State require river crossing, an average canoe sailing speed obtained by field measurements in Cross River State was applied to respective river segments.

In this study, the wet season road data was prepared separately from the dry season considering the seasonality of road accessibility due to flooding. To create a wet season road network, potentially flooded road segments were delineated using 3 km buffer from the main river channel, to capture the 212 flood-prone communities in Cross River State (Vanguard Nigeria, 2013). Road segments within the buffer region were assigned the average canoe sailing speed (Figure 4). This study assumes that people will alight from cars and cross the flooded road segment using canoes or the driving speed will reduce to an average canoe sailing speed.

Figure 4: The maps show 3 km flood regimes in CRS. The map on the left indicates potential flooding at senatorial district level while the map to right represents LGA level.

Communities and population

Locations of communities (villages) were obtained from the Office of the Surveyor-General Cross River State (OSG-CRS). Population census figures for 1991 were received from the National Population Commission (NPC) Cross River State. The figures were projected to 2015 since there was no recent census data at the community level. The projected population figures were matched with the communities' data to produce communities' locations with population figures. Since there was no age attribute in the population data, the percentage of women within child-bearing age (15-49) in Cross River State (26.5%) was used to estimate maternal population in each of the communities.

This study believes that socio-environment factors influence access to healthcare. Therefore, elevation data were obtained from the United States Geological Surveys (USGS) Earth Explorer. Elevation values were rescaled to standard digital number of electromagnetic spectrum (-1 to 9), since its original values were from -1 to 9,000.

Drive times were measured from communities' centroid to facilities, using the ArcGIS Network Analyst tool. The source of the trip was community centroid and the destination was the nearest PHC, assuming that patients would use the nearest health facilities (McLaren et al., 2014; Stock, 1983). Wet and dry seasons access were mapped separately considering the variations in wet season's road networks due to flooding.

Whereas a previous UK study calculated socioeconomic deprivation based on the indices of multiple deprivation (IMD 2004) scores (Jones et al., 2010), this present study used literacy (education level) and car ownership (preferred travel scenarios) scores as proxies for socioeconomic deprivation in Cross River State. It was assumed that education level and car ownership, especially in urban areas are linked to small-area socioeconomic deprivation (Christie & Fone, 2003; Havard et al., 2008). This study assumes that trekking is linked to low-income households and while car ownership of family car is related to high-income households. Therefore, poorer communities were expected to have higher trekking scores than the wealthier communities and similar relationship was expected for car ownership.

LGA level Literacy and preferred travel scenario data were obtained from the Cross River State Socio-economic survey of 2013 (Ayara et al., 2013). Literacy data had a single attribute (literacy score) while preferred travel scenario was multiple including; trekking, bicycle, personal motorcycle, commercial motorcycle, family car and commercial car. Since socio-economic data was only available at LGA, small-area deprivation score at community level was calculated by multiplying each variable score by the proportion of population on each community, assuming that the level deprivation would increase by the number of people residing in the area.

Statistical analyses were undertaken using SPSS for Windows version 22. Pearson's product moment correlation coefficient was fitted through drive times to PHC and elevation of the

community, to examine interactions of physical environment with accessibility. Drive times to PHC being the dependent variable was measured in minutes from home of resident to the nearest health facility. Based on evidence from elsewhere that area deprivation can act to compound issues of poor access to healthcare (Havard et al., 2008), interactions between deprivation and accessibility measure (drive time) were examined by fitting interaction terms between quartiles of deprivation and accessibility. Independent variables (socio-environmental factors) were elevation and small-area deprivation (literacy, trekking, bicycle, personal motorcycle, commercial motorcycle, family car and commercial car). As there are evidences elsewhere that seasons act to worsen access to healthcare accessibility in deprived communities (Ewing et al., 2016; Oppong, 1996), analyses were split into wet and dry seasons.

Results and Discussion

Results

A total of 119 PHCs were mapped and included in the study (Figure 5). Akamkpa Local Government Area tends to have fewer facilities probably because of the National Park there. The health facilities appear to be well linked to the road network in the state (Figure 6).

Figure 5: PHCs in Cross River State

Figure 6: PHCs and road roads in Cross River State

Table 1: Population and access to healthcare

Distribution	Population	Dry season access (min)	Wet Season access (min)	Difference (%)
Minimum	7	0.1	0.1	0 (0)
Mean	939 (SD 3049)	41.1 (SD 31.4)	57.7 (SD 62.2)	16.6 (28.8)
Maximum	55,134	156.5	493.9	337.4 (68.3)
Total	961,635	42,057.5	59,038.1	16,980.6 (28.8)

Total number of communities = 1024. Rate of population travel per drive time calculated as total population divided by total distance = 23 persons/minute in dry season and 16 persons/minute in wet season. Percentage difference calculated difference seasons divided by wet season and multiplied by 100.

Travel times and demographics

The measured average driving and canoe sailing speeds in Cross River State were 19.26 km/hr and 3.3 km/hr, respectively, while average driving speed from Google map was 21.6 km/h. The difference may be attributed to the traffic situation of the roads when measurements were taken which did not affect Google measurements. Communities in the study were 1024 and the population within maternal age was 961,635 (Table 1). The range of maternal population was 55,127 (7 - 55,134), the average was 939 (SD 3049), though most communities had a maternal population between 7 – 1000 (Figure 5).

Access to maternal health services in PHCs

In the dry season, the minimum, maximum and average drive times to the nearest facility were 0.1 minutes, 56.5 minutes and 41.1 minutes (SD 31.4), respectively (Table 1). The total drive times of the population from 1024 communities to the nearest PHC was 42, 057.5 minutes and the rate of maternal travel to facilities was 23 women per minute.

In the wet season, the minimum, maximum and average drive times were 0.1 minutes, 493.9 minutes and 57.7 minutes (SD 62.2), respectively, indicating 1.4 times increase in average drive time and 3.2-fold increase in maximum drive time compared to the dry season (Table 1). The total drive times to facilities in the wet season was 59,038.1 minutes. We found that average, maximum and total drive times in the wet season compared to the dry season increased by 16.6 minutes (SD 30.8), 337.4 and 16,980.4 minutes, respectively. Also, the rate of maternal travel per

minute declined from 23 women in the dry season to 16 women in the wet season, indicating a 30% decline in the access to maternal healthcare in the wet season (Table 1).

Figure 7: Seasonal access to healthcare in Cross River State.

Area deprivation and access to maternal healthcare

The central part and fringes of Cross River State had more women who travelled over 90 minutes to the facilities (Figure 7). Women who lived in the densely populated communities which are mostly urban, spent less time to reach the facilities unlike those in the sparsely populated rural communities (Figures 8 and 9). However, a community with population up to 10,000, travelled about 130 minutes in the dry season and 290 minutes in the wet season (Figures 8 and 9). In some locations, for instance a community in Calabar (the state capital), the level of urbanisation and infrastructural development did not reduce travel time in the wet season. Figures 8 and 9, show a community with population 55,000 which drive times increased from 10 minutes in the dry season to 25 minutes in the wet season.

Figure 8: Population and dry season access

Figure 9: Population and Wet season access

Facilities distribution and accessibility

A total of 119 PHCs were included in the study (Table 2). The facilities were unequally distributed across the three senatorial districts with the majority (53) in CSD, 40 in SSD and 26 in NSD. This present study revealed that a fewer number of facilities were in SSD though it is the most populated district in the state.

Maternal healthcare accessibility was limited in the wet season compared to the dry season (Table 2). Less than half of SSD facilities (32.5%) were accessible while nearly half (43.7%) of CSD facilities were inaccessible in the wet season. The ratios of facilities to population were down by nearly half in CSD and CRS, and two-third in SSD in the wet season. The number of facilities available for the population declined by 67.1% in the SSD, 9.8% in the CSD and 43.6% in the CRS during the wet season. However, geographical access was same throughout the year in the NSD since it is unaffected by the seasonal flooding in the wet season.

Table 2: Facilities accessibility

Locality	Population	Facilities access			Facilities per 100,000 women		
		Dry Season (%)	Wet Season (%)	Difference (%)	Dry Season	Wet Season	Difference (%)
SSD	573103	40 (100)	13 (32.5)	27 (67.7)	7.0	2.3	4.7 (67.1)
NSD	133155	26 (100)	26 (100)	-	19.5	19.5	-
CSD	254289	53 (100)	28 (52.8)	25 (47.2)	20.8	11.0	9.8 (47.1)
CRS	961635	119 (100)	67 (56.3)	52 (43.7)	12.4	7.0	5.4 (43.6)

Percentage difference calculated as the difference between dry and wet season divided by dry season value and multiplied by 100.

Geographical accessibility of facilities and area deprivation

The included variables relate to either socio-economic or topographic characteristics of the communities. Socioeconomic variable relating to education level of women was the literacy score and transport were travels by trekking, bicycle, personal motorcycle, commercial motorcycle, family car and commercial car.

In the dry season, only 6% of the variance in the dependent variable was explained by the independent variables and was statistically significant (Table 3). Among the independent variables in the model, only use of personal motorcycle, use of family car and topography were statistically significant. One unit of change in the use of personal motorcycle led to 850.2 minutes' decrease (SD -0.04) of drive times, indicating a decline in drive times to maternal health facilities as ownership of personal motorcycle increases (Table 3). A unit increase in topography also led to 25.8 minutes' decrease (SD -0.14) in drive times, implying the higher the topography the less the drive times to facilities (Table 3).

Table 3: Relationships in the dry season analysis

Variables (Predictors)	Mean (SD)	B	S.E.	Beta	t	p-value	Confidence Interval
(Constant)	-	61.11	4.12	-	14.83	0.00	53.03 - 69.20
Literacy score	0.85 (0.30)	-1.33	78.24	-0.01	-0.02	0.99	-154.86 - 152.20
Trekking score	0.61 (0.16)	-40.98	59.13	0.21	-0.69	0.49	-157.01 - 75.05
Bicycle use score	0.00 (0.01)	-853.76	677.56	0.17	-1.26	0.21	-2183.34 - 475.82
Personal motorcycle use score	0.00 (0.02)	-850.22	302.70	0.41	-2.81	0.01	-1444.20 – (-256.24)
Commercial motorcycle use score	0.01 (0.02)	249.43	134.59	0.15	1.85	0.06	-14.68 - 513.54
Family car use	0.01 (0.06)	391.43	94.73	0.77	4.13	0.00	205.55 - 577.31
Commercial car use	0.02 (0.11)	-81.84	93.53	0.28	-0.88	0.38	-265.37 - 101.69
Topography	0.65 (0.17)	-25.81	6.023	0.14	-4.29	0.00	-37.63 – (-13.99)

Model Summary: $R = 0.260^a$, $R\text{ Square} = 0.67$, $\text{Adjusted } R\text{ Square} = 0.060$ and $\text{Std. Error of the Estimate} = 30.433$. Anova^a: $F = 9.173$ and $\text{Sig. } 0.000^b$. Where a = Dependent variables (drive times) and b = Predictor variables. S.E. = Standard Error (B). Beta = Standard deviation from B.

In the wet season, 74% ($\text{Adjusted } R\text{ Square} = 0.74$) of the variance in the dependent variable was explained by the independent variables and the model was statistically significant (Table 4). The independent variable that were statistically significant are; literacy score, trekking score, bicycle use score, commercial motorcycle use score, use of commercial car and topography. Unlike the dry season, the use of family was no longer significant in the wet season. A unit increase in literacy score was accompanied by 543.8 minutes ($B = -543.8$, $SD\ 2.6$) decrease in drive times. A unit rise in the number of women who commute by walking led to 301.7 minutes' ($B=301.7$, $SD=0.8$) increase in drive times. As use of bicycle increases by a unit, drive times increased by 3309.4 minutes ($B=3309.4$, $SD =0.3$). A unit increase in the use of commercial motorcycle also increased drive times by 854.5 minutes ($B= 854.5$, $SD =0.3$). As the use of

commercial car increased by a unit, drive times also increased by 591.3 minutes (B=591.3, SD=1.0). However, a unit increase in topography decreased drive times by 97.8 minutes (B= -97.7, SD = -0.27).

Table 4: Relationship in the wet season analysis

Variables	Mean (SD)	B	S. E	Beta	t	p-value	Confidence Interval
(Constant)	-	124.59	8.18	-	15.23	.00	108.53 - 140.64
Literacy score	0.85 (0.30)	-54.84	16.28	-2.58	-3.50	0.00	-848.54- (-239.13)
Trekking score	0.61 (0.16)	301.74	117.36	0.77	2.57	0.01	71.45 - 532.03
Bicycle use score	0.001 (0.006)	3309.36	1344.74	0.32	2.46	0.01	670.58 - 5948.14
Personal motorcycle use score	0.004 (0.015)	5.36	600.75	0.00	0.01	0.99	-1173.49 - 1184.21
Commercial motorcycle use score	0.01 (0.02)	854.52	267.12	0.26	3.20	0.001	330.36 - 1378.67
Family car use	0.01 (0.06)	345.02	188.00	0.34	1.84	0.07	-23.89 - 713.93
Commercial car use	0.02 (0.11)	591.34	185.62	0.99	3.19	0.01	227.10 - 955.58
Topography	0.65 (0.17)	-97.76	11.96	-0.27	-8.18	0.00	-121.22 -74.31

Model Summary: R = 0.283^a, R square = 0.081, Adjusted R Square = 0.74 and Std Error of Estimate = 60.401. Anova^a: F = 11.153 and Sig. = 0.000^b. Where a = Dependent variables (drive times) and b = Predictor variables. S.E. = Standard Error (B). Beta = Standard deviation from B.

Discussion

Access to BEmONC in PHCs

This study attempts to fill the research gap in the area of access to maternal health services especially, BEmONC, which is one of the leading causes of high maternal and child mortality in developing countries, including Nigeria. Previous studies have measured geographical access by travel distance or time. Travel distance measurements include Euclidean distance and road distance (Ayeni et al., 1987; Stock, 1983). Some studies have also conducted similar research using drive times and walking times (Jordan et al., 2004; Zwarenstein et al., 2014). In this study, travels to BEmONC was measured by drive times with the assumption that pregnant women would be unable to walk longer distances to health facilities. Although pregnant women may walk to nearby health facilities at the early stage of pregnancy, that might be difficult at the later stage, and during labour. Therefore, driving is the most suitable method of measuring geographical access the BEmONC.

Unlike previous studies which measured individuals' travel times to health facilities (Alegana et al., 2012; Blanford et al., 2012), this present study measured drive times from the centroid of each community to the nearest facility. Therefore, our findings do not represent individual access but that of the community. Although measurements were conducted at individual community level, the results were aggregated and presented at senatorial districts and state levels to simplify findings. Measurement of access at community level is uncommon in health literature due to study design selection. Most epidemiological studies, except for ecological study would measure trips at individual levels since their data are mostly collected at individual level. Ecological design adopted in this study is advantageous because of data suitability and representation of the whole population.

Seasonal geographical access to Basis Emergency Obstetric Newborn Care

Like a few previous studies (Ewing et al., 2016; Oppong, 1996), this study recognised the importance of seasonal changes on human activities including travels to healthcare. In this present study, the percentage differences in mean drive times to EmONC in the wet and dry seasons was 28.8%, indicating about one-third increase in travel time to the facilities in the wet season. At the state level, the ratio of facilities to 100,000 women in the wet season declined by a percentage difference of 43.6% compared to the dry season, while 43.7% of the facilities were inaccessible. In the support of the findings of this, a study found that while 87% of pregnant women lived within one hour to the nearest primary care centre, the value dropped to 5% in the wet season in Mozambique (Makanga et al., 2017b). Therefore, previous estimations of access that did not

consider seasonal variability would have underestimated access to maternal health services in the wet season.

We found that the impact of the wet season on the access to BEmONC varied across the senatorial districts of the state with the least effect in the NSD and worst effect in the SSD. Similarly, seasonal access to health care is expected to vary according to output unit (e.g. community, senatorial district and state level) depending on the level of development. Thus, the developed countries would feel less impact of the wet season on healthcare access due to infrastructural development and use of alternative means of transport such as helicopters when roads are inaccessible.

Factors access to BEmONC

Spatial epidemiology looks at the risk factors that are associated with health outcomes. Risk factors often considered are environmental and a non-environmental factor. Environmental factors include season; transport (Makanga et al., 2017b) and natural disaster (Curtis et al., 2009). Non-environmental factors include deprivation which covers income and education (Cromley & McLafferty, 2002; Curtis et al., 2009). This study considers environmental and non-environmental factors in the communities that have relationships with geographical access to healthcare. The factors in the study were; literacy, elevation, population, car ownership and use of public and private bicycle, motorcycles and public transport.

While some studies consider factors relating to individual that need the service, we looked at the characteristics of the locations. The residential location of the woman is an important indication of socio-economic status and access to essential services like healthcare. In Nigeria, urban areas are more developed and equipped with public infrastructures than the rural areas, residents of urban areas would likely access more services than those in the rural areas. On that note, this study esteemed location characteristics higher than the individual characteristics in the access to BEmONC.

This study also looked at the relationship between accessibility (drive times to the facilities) and means of transport available to the population in the study. Commercial transport was more likely to be used than personal transports in the wet season, probably because of the fear of damage to personal cars. We also found that literacy and topography had higher negative relationships with drive times to healthcare in the wet season. Which implies, the higher the level of literacy and topography the shorter the distance to the facilities. Therefore, the distance a woman travels healthcare may be dependent of the level of education of the community she lives.

Summary and Conclusion

This study examined seasonal geographical access to prenatal and BEmONC. In overall, access to maternal healthcare was poorer in the wet season and the population is expected to make extra budget for healthcare at such times. Healthcare access was potentially interrupted in wet seasons that is prone to diseases spread. Health planners should make adequate preparation to transport pregnant women within potentially flooded locations and individuals must budget extra time when seeking healthcare in the wet season.

Inequality of access to maternal healthcare was prominent in two major variables namely; education and high topography. Facilities accessibility was more favourable to women who lived in high literacy or high topography communities. Therefore, access to healthcare can be significantly influenced by literacy and topography. It also found that public transport was potentially the most reliable means of transport in the wet season compared to use to private vehicles.

It is expected that access to maternal health services such as prenatal and BEmONC would improve especially in the wet season if planners and research communities consider the findings and recommendation of this study.

This study considered only one component of access to healthcare which is geographical access. Since geographical access is not the only factor influencing healthcare, we recognise that other factors are equally important in the planning of population access to healthcare. However, geographical would boost other factors if considered at the planning stage.

There is an awareness that people may not always use the closest health facility. However, since previous studies have found distance decay in the utilisation of healthcare, the findings of this study remain valid. Our model assumed that average drive time would reduce to average canoe sailing speed on the flooded road segments. However, our model remains a valid estimation of wet season travel since the data used in the model were obtained from actual measurements.

Like UK Data service, the government of Nigeria should fund and maintain a reliable open data source for research. Although, data availability was a major problem of this research, this study successfully used the available data to measure geographical access to healthcare. Health planners should prioritise data collection and consider seasonal accessibility of access at the planning stage of healthcare interventions.

Without good infrastructures, the effectiveness of health facilities may decline. Therefore, health interventions planning should include infrastructural developments such as road network and drainage system especially in the rural areas. In the wet season, mobile clinics should be made available to affected communities and suitable water ambulances should be provided for free or at a reduced cost.

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